

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Contested History and Struggling Lives: Reading *A Bend in the River* as a Narrative of Change and Disorder

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ABSTRACT

History is constructed by those in power and is shaped by memory, perspectives, and subjective truth. It can be fragmented, contested, and chaotic, marked by the transition from colonial rule to post-independence, from traditional to modern living, and by the struggle for survival and the relentless escape from the void. Naipaul has depicted postcolonial societies and their struggles in his novels. The present novel, *Bend in the River*, is set in an African society marred by chaos and disorder after the withdrawal of colonial forces and depicts the problems associated with the new order and militant forces. It showcases the struggles and difficult lives of migrants and diasporic people who want to achieve something but are caught in the chaos of changing circumstances in a foreign land. This paper, therefore, attempts to bring out the negotiation of colonial history, subjective history and postcolonial history- thereby revealing their intersections. While doing so, the narrative reflects the universal human predicament, migration, and the search for meaning amid navigating phases of change and disorder.

Keywords: History, Post-colonial, Africa, Violence, Migration

FULL RESEARCH PAPER**Introduction**

The oeuvre of Sir V.S. Naipaul holds an extremely important place in contemporary literature. A novelist and non-fiction writer, his works explore suppressed histories and consider the predicament of marginalised and uprooted multitudes. Through his literary works, Naipaul explores ideas, engages with present situations and envisions the future. While revolving around the portrayal of the socio-political background, economic conditions and cultural and historical specifics of colonial and post-colonial societies, his writings represent and seek to bring to the centre the marginalised and subaltern characters living at the periphery of society. Naipaul has written extensively on Third World countries. The present novel, *A Bend in the River*, is one of the masterpieces of the novelist. African nationalism, political instability and the endangered lives of Indians and foreigners are among the novel's key themes. The novel, to some extent, is based on Naipaul's observations of Zaire (present-day Democratic Republic of the Congo) and East Africa. In 1965, Zaire was governed by Joseph Mobutu for 32 years. Mobutu became the basis of the Big Man, the President, and a dictator. Through him, Naipaul represents an autocratic ruler and his nature of governing the lives of post-colonial Africans by control and oppression.

The River as History

The novel has been structured into four parts: The Second Rebellion, The New Domain, The Big Man, and Battle. All of these divisions mark different stages in the socio-political development and transformation of the African town. The opening lines of the novel, "The world is what it is; men who are nothing, who allow themselves to become nothing, have no place in it" (BITR 3), have a deeper meaning. Interpreting these lines, William Vincent points out that they not only hint at the recent events that become history but also foreground the process of making history (337). Therefore, the opening sentence refers to linear time, understood as a sequential progression of events over a period of time. In the title, the river serves as a metaphor for change and flow, leading to movement and progression. Bend symbolises a shift in direction, again leading to progression, though towards new trajectories. These words, when taken together, insinuate an upcoming transformation. Vincent also thinks of the river as history, with the bend representing a significant moment that influences the course of history and leads to change once more. "The river, I think, is history itself, and the bend in the river is history in the process of changing direction" (337). Interestingly, Naipaul chooses not to name the river, the town, or even the President, which

universalises the narrative and keeps it unhinged from a specific geographical space. Again, references to several cities such as London, Canada, Uganda, Italy, Australia, Switzerland, and Paris have been made here and there, which situates the novel within a broader framework- a cosmopolitan framework. Set in a small, unnamed African country after independence, the novel explores the fragmentation, conflicts, and uncertainties surrounding events there.

Colonial History

In the novel, Naipaul repeatedly brings up Europeans and mentions that history has been constructed by those in power, the Europeans. Denny Joseph and Siny Jose argue that "It has been demonstrated that history falls prey to the imperial motives of colonisation and exploitation of the 'non-Western Other.' Whatever version of history is in the limelight is the one that has power, and may be assimilated as an integral part of the history of tomorrow." (2). This statement holds in Salim's case as well. The history of people like Salim's family is buried and forgotten by the next generation. This makes him question their identity and existence. "We simply lived; we did what was expected of us, what we had seen the previous generation do. We never asked why; we never recorded. We felt in our bones that we were very old people, but we seemed to have no means of gauging the passing of time" (BITR 12). Unfortunately, Salim doesn't have any family stories except one told by his grandfather, about him having shipped a boatful of slaves. Whatever knowledge he acquired was from books written by Europeans. To quote, "All that I know of our history and the history of the Indian Ocean I have got from books written by Europeans" (BITR 13). In fact, he thought that Europeans had chronicled their past and saved it. "Without Europeans, I feel, all our past would have been washed away, like the scuff- marks of fishermen on the beach outside our town" (BITR 13). However, Salim was well aware of the Europeans' motives. He opines that Europeans were intelligent and powerful people who not only colonised them but also wanted to be seen as doing good things for the slaves (BITR 19). Even Raymond, the historian and a European, has a colonial mindset. He has written about Africa, but he had less knowledge and less feeling about his subject. (BITR 210). In his article about the race riot, though the subject was an event in Africa, he did not get to the real facts; he got stuck with the newspapers.

In the novel, we have characters like Ferdinand and Indar who are shaped by Western education. For instance, Zabeth, who lives a traditional African life, wants something different and better for her son. She wants Ferdinand to learn manners and ways of the world. That's why she brings her son to Salim, who knows English and is a foreigner. He is a boarder at the Lycee. In the novel, lycee serves as an important

colonial representative of education. It is a European-style school that ignores local and traditional history and culture. It was through the lycee that students like Ferdinand gained identity, thereby shifting them from locals to elites and later to participants in greater political power.

Even after the colonial forces withdrew, Europe continued to rule the Africans through its language and goods. Salim remarks, "Europe no longer rules. But it still fed us in a hundred ways with its language, and sent us its increasingly wonderful goods, things which, in the bush of Africa, added year by year to our idea of who we were, gave us that idea of our modernity and development, and made us aware of another Europe- the Europe of great cities, great stores. Great buildings, great universities" (BITR 268-269).

Post-Independence History

Leela Gandhi views postcolonialism "...as a theoretical resistance to the mystifying amnesia of the colonial aftermath" (4). In the light of this novel, it can be read as a narrative that reveals the consequences of postcolonial "amnesia," in which the failure to critically engage with the colonial past can lead to instability, disorder, and fragile identities. After colonial withdrawal, there is chaos and disorder in the town. Fanon rightly observes, "Decolonisation, which sets out to change the order of the world, is, obviously, a programme of complete disorder" (27). There is execution and bloodshed in the first part of the novel. In the eyes of Salim, "The place had had its troubles: the town at the bend in the river was more than half destroyed. What had been the European suburb near the rapids had been burnt down, and bush had grown over the ruins; it was harder to distinguish what had been gardens from what had been streets" (BITR 5). Being among the ruins, Salim loses his time-sense. He feels that the place has already seen its future. This line hints at the brutal fate of the future, wherein everything will be marked by decay and deconstruction. Progression requires movement, and things cannot remain stagnant for long. The town also returned to normal once the peace was restored. And the business starts up again. And so does Salim's shop, which he got from Nazruddin.

At independence, the people of the town get mad with anger. "The people of our region had been much abused, not only by the Europeans and Arabs, but also by other Africans; and at independence, they had refused to be ruled by the new government in the capital. It was an instinctive uprising, without leaders or a manifesto" (BITR 75). The war was around, and disorder was prevalent. There are ambushes on the road, villages are attacked, and officials are killed. Classes are

suspended at the lycee, and the town is put under army control. Salim observes that in post-colonial Africa, everybody could get guns, and every tribe could be a warrior tribe. But the soldiers never showed their weapons and were kept short of equipment. This was a way for the new President to control and police the country. (BITR 77) The new President doesn't play. They shoot Colonel Yenyi in front of women and everybody, and Iyanda, the Sergeant. Notably, the new president is behaving like a colonial government, trying to control and manage the masses with his power. To quote Salim,

The President had sent terror to our town and region. But at the same time, by terrorising the army as well, he was making a gesture to the local people. The news of the executions would have spread fast, and people would already have become confused and nervous. They would have felt- as I began to feel- that for the first time since independence there was some guiding intelligence in the capital, and that the free- for – all of independence had come to an end. (Salim 87)

There are instances of a fighter plane flying overhead and releasing missiles into the bush.

However, soon after, a period of economic boom comes, and things change. Projects start, and numerous government departments come to life again. The airfield is recommissioned, and extended buses and taxis start running. Consequently, cities get populated, and new ones are built. Business starts running, and the hotel and the Hellenic Club fill with salesmen, mostly Europeans, while steamers bring European builders for construction. The same bush which makes them depressed in the days of rebellion excites them now, once the order is restored in the town. Further, the bush near rapids is cleared and taken by the government and named as Domain, as "He was creating an area where he and his flag were supreme. As an African, he was building a new town on the site of what had been a rich European suburb- but what he was building was meant to be grander" (BITR 115-116). Actually, the President wishes to create a Modern Africa- replacing traditional Africa- of villages and bushes with a version of Africa that has everything that makes other countries modern. In this way, he is transforming Africa into a new Africa. Soon, it will have a university city and a research centre. It has a polytechnic and dormitories too. Raymond, the Historian, praises the President and says, "He's disciplined the army and brought peace to this land of many peoples. It is possible once again to traverse the country from one end to the other-something the colonial power thought it alone had brought about" (BITR

154). These lines undoubtedly hint at the colonial nature of the President's control over the country.

As the novel progresses, we see violent outbursts and riots among the masses. The statue of the African Madonna and child is smashed. Bloodshed and violence directed against the authorities become common. People get killed by police and rioters. People like Zabeth and Salim are fearful. The Bush is again at war, and the army is kidnapping young men.

Subjective History and Identity- Crisis

In Preface to *The Location of Culture*, Bhabha observes that Naipaul's characters have 'unpromising lives' and are well aware of the complex and fragmentary structure of their societies and the loss of their cultural order. Yet they succeed in leaving their mark on the world. (xii) Salim is no exception to this. Salim is an Indian Muslim belonging to a family of repute. He lives in Africa, but his people are not African. He belongs to the East Coast, which was not truly African, but rather a conglomeration of Arabs, Indians, Persians and Portuguese. Regarding his family, Salim says, "My family was Muslim. But we were a special group. We were distinct from the Arabs and other Muslims of the coast; in our customs and attitudes, we were closer to the Hindus of north-western India, from which we had originally come" (BITR 12). His people originally came from North-western India. But Salim don't know when they came as for him, "We were not that kind of people" (BITR 12). But on the other hand, he thought of his people as simply living, unable to stand back and ponder the nature of their lives.

Salim is like Mr Biswas. Just like Mr Biswas, who wants to 'paddle his own canoe', Salim wants to leave his mark in the world. In fact, the very opening lines of the work, "The world is what it is; men who are nothing, who allow themselves to become nothing, have no place in it" (BITR 3), talk about action rather than relaxing and thinking. Salim utters these lines. From a very small age, Salim developed the habit of looking at things from a distance, as a detached observer, and his insecurity began. However, he wishes to stand apart from his family. He is anxious about the future- of being forgotten and washed away. He wants to 'make good'. But he doesn't have any skills or talents beyond the African trading skills of his family. And that's why he grabs the offer of Nazruddin, offering a shop in a far-off African town ruled by European power. The novel begins with Salim's journey from the East Coast to deep inside Africa. Salim is in search of life, and he has to start afresh, but as he gets deeper, he feels, "There can't be a new life at the end of this" (BITR 4). Salim thinks of himself

as an 'outsider' in the town. Neither 'settler nor visitor', just people with no place to go. To quote:

We were simple men with civilisations but without other homes. Whenever we were allowed to, we did the occasional things we had to do, like the ants. We had the occasional comfort of reward, but in good times or bad, we lived with the knowledge that we were expendable, that our labour might at any moment go to waste, that we ourselves might be smashed up, and that others would replace us. To us, that was the painful part, that others would come at a better time. But we were like the ants; we kept on. (BITR 100)

In the midst of the boom, too, Salim has his anxieties and becomes restless as he was at the beginning. He sees a future for a country full of disorder. He becomes jealous when he learns that Ferdinand has been sent on a government scholarship to the polytechnic. Explaining the reason for his jealousy, Salim says, "I was jealous more of that idea he had always had of his importance, his glamour". (BITR 119).

When Indar returns to the town for a term at the Polytechnic, Salim compares himself with him and remarks, "I couldn't be any other way with Indar. He had always made me feel so backwards" (BITR 127). However, when he goes with him to the Domain, he feels that he does not belong in that world. Later, at the party at Domain, Salim thinks he has found the kind of life he wants. To quote him, "I never wanted to be ordinary again. I felt that by some piece of luck I had stumbled on the equivalent of what years before Nazruddin had found right here" (BITR 149). Salim is depressed after seeing Nazruddin in good spirits, too. He thinks that he won't be able to catch him, and his life would always be unsatisfactory.

King remarks, "In Naipaul's novel, the central characters are not protected by imperial power and their lives are endangered by the rapid changes and instabilities of postcolonial Africa" (119). Soon after the rebellion in the town, as violence becomes prevalent, Salim becomes aware of his limitations and considers escape. Later, we learn that Salim goes to London, but he is confused there as well. He has gone to London for relief and rescue, but he is anxious there. When he returns to the town, he learns that the President has taken his shop under the guise of Radicalisation and given it to Citizen Theotime. To make more money, he deals in gold and ivory, but he is imprisoned and brought before the Commissioner, who is none other than Ferdinand. On his suggestion, Salim leaves the town and sets out on his own journey. Therefore, throughout the novel, Salim suffers through pangs of identity crisis and uncertainty.

The same view is shared by Indar as well. Indar belongs to a rich family- his grandfather had come from Punjab to work as a contract labourer in railways, and then he got settled on the coast and became a moneylender. Indar is going to England to pursue a three- year course. But he opines that, "We're washed up here, you know. To be in Africa, you have to be strong. We're not strong. We don't even have a flag' (BITR 21). Later, we find that, though he becomes a lecturer and well-bred, he is unable to live the life of his dreams. When he visits the Indian High Commission, he gets a clear sense of his roots. Soon, he has a major self-realisation that he belongs only to himself. "I belonged to myself alone. I was going to surrender my manhood to nobody. For someone like me, there was only one civilisation and one place- London, or a place like it" (BITR 175). He realises his value and says to Salim, "I don't want to pass. I know exactly who I am and where I stand in the world. But now I want to win and win and win" (BITR 180). He goes to America, to New York, but remains unsatisfied and often thinks of going home. Shobha, Mahesh's wife, is also unsatisfied with her life. She comes from a well-to-do family, but she regrets having wasted her life. While talking to Salim, she says, "Carry on, carry on. That's all I've been doing. That's how I've spent my life. That's how I've lived in this place, among Africans. Is that a life, Salim?" (BITR 82) Yvette's position is not better either. She is a European and Raymond's wife. But she is a stranger in the town and was 'doubly dependent'. She has a good relationship with Indar, and after Indar moves, she gets involved in a sexual relationship with Salim. Describing her uncertain life and situation, she says, "My life is still fluid. I must do something. I just can't stay here" (BITR 222).

Change and Escape

The novel abounds with narratives of change and flux. Nothing is certain, and fear and confusion are prevalent. In Uganda, Nazruddin's place of shelter, a king is overthrown who flies to a new place. Now there is news of tribal and racial troubles, and Nazruddin moves out to Canada, and then he moves to England. Noimon, the Greek business, has sold up and left for Australia. Zabeth has to leave her business. Metty constantly tries to upgrade himself. Mahesh tries his hand at new businesses. Shobha is frustrated and wants to go to Paris for skin treatment. Father Huisman is killed. Raymond and Yvette leave Domain. Salim is imprisoned. Death, decay, violence, and change are dominant throughout the novel. In particular, the novel's first part foregrounds themes of destruction and transformation. Towards the end of the novel, we find that the same atmosphere of violence and destruction prevails, though this time Africa is Modern Africa, ruled by a President. Talking about the general condition of people in the town, Ferdinand says to Salim, "We all are going to hell, and every

man knows this in his bones. We're being killed. Nothing has any meaning. That is why everyone is so frantic. Everyone wants to make their money and run away. But where? That is what is driving people mad" (BITR 319). These lines suggest that a sense of fear and frenzy pervades the novel's final part.

Escape and flight are two of the motifs of the novel. Salim, who had fled from the coast, wants to escape from the town. Indar had gone to London, to the University, and after his short stay at Domain, he flew again. By using the metaphor of an aeroplane, Indar points towards the escapist tendency of people like him. He says, "You are still in one place when you arrive at the other. The aeroplane is faster than the heart. You arrive quickly, and you leave quickly. You don't grieve much." (BITR 130). Complexity and confusion add to the universal theme of the text that every society and system therein goes through a process of change- change from old order into new, from being ruled by colonial masters to gaining independence, from dictatorship to democracy, from change to stability and vice versa. Commenting on the uncertain nature of lives, Salim remarks, "But in the town, where all was arbitrary, and the law was what it was, all our lives were fluid. None of us had certainties of any kind. Without always knowing what we were doing, we constantly adjusted to the arbitrariness around us. In the end, we couldn't say where we stood" (BITR 223).

Conclusion

The novel *A Bend in the River* operates across three layers of history: colonial, post-independence, and subjective. By intersecting these histories, Naipaul has revealed the complexities and intricacies of lives involved, along with their confusions, fears and anxieties. The novelist has depicted a stark conflict between Traditional African life and Free African Life, and Old Africa and New Africa. By highlighting these differences, he has painted a picture of fragmented, struggling lives amid the several phases of socio-political transformation across geographical territories, marked by change, disorder, and violence. As the novel progresses, confusion, the arbitrariness of human life, and uncertainty deepen, giving the text a universal dimension.

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Works Cited

Bhabha, Homi K. *The Location of Culture*. 1994. London: Routledge, 2017.

Fanon, Frantz. *The Wretched of the Earth*. Trans. Constance Ferrington. 1963. London: Penguin Books, 2001. Print.

King, Bruce. *V. S. Naipaul*. 2nd ed. London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2003.

Joseph, Denny and Sini Jose. "Reinventing Histories: A Postcolonial Revisiting of Colonial Historiography". *International Journal of English Language, Education and Literature Studies*. Vol-4, Issue-3, May-Jun 2025. 1–6.

Naipaul, V.S. *A Bend in the River*. 1979. London: Picador, 2011.

Gandhi, Leela. *Postcolonial Theory: A Critical Introduction*. Oxford UP, 2001.

Vincent, William. "Naipaul's *A Bend In The River*: Time, History, And "Africa". *Journal of South Asian Literature*, Vol. 26, No. 1/2, 1991, pp 337–349. *JSTOR*, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40873258> . Accessed 25 March. 2026.

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